

Validation Results at the DSs in Czech Republic (a) and Spain (b)

Deliverable 6.2

Submission Date: 30 October 2021

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

WP6 proposes a "start to end" valorisation process of the urban sewage sludge (USS) and organic fraction from municipal solid waste (OFMSW) to obtain ready-to-use products. Different processes will be studied to demonstrate the feasibility to obtain high-value products from raw biowastes (OFMSW and USS). These processes will be validated in prototypes operated in three demonstration sites (DS): DS 1 (ES), DS6 (CZ) and D57 (NL). Special attention will be given to the key operation parameters and system design for the production of target valuable end-products to be adapted at DSs.

The focus of this deliverable is to analyse and discuss the results gathered in the Demo Sites located in Czech Republic (a) and Spain (b).

The advanced anaerobic digestion pilot plant located in Spain (b) treats primary and secondary sludge (mixed sludge) produced in the Estiviel Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) located in DS1 (Spain) through a two-staged bio-electrochemical route (Dual Anaerobic Digestion). This process aims to obtain high quality biogas and biosolids with enhanced sanitation properties for land application. The decentralised anaerobic digestion for treating sludge from small and isolated populations, also located in (b), is also being tested. Also, an advanced sludge pre-thickening system was tested at DS1.

The bio-electrochemical system (BES) target is to bio-electrochemically convert the CO₂ contained in the biogas produced from the digestion of USS sludge or OFMSW into valuable organic compounds. This prototype has been tested in DS 1 (Spain) treating biogas from OFMSW and has already been installed DS 6 (Czech Republic (a)), treating biogas from USS.

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